

**Locals, Newcomers, and Longtimers: How Business Owners Navigate Culture and
Commerce in *Gentefying Barrios* of Southern California**

Equal Authorship
Yael Shmaryahu-Yeshurun, Ph.D.
Assistant Professor
Department of Politics and Government
Ben-Gurion University of the Negev
yaelshma@post.bgu.ac.il

Janet Muñoz, Ph.D. (corresponding author)
Assistant Professor
Department of Sociology
California State University, Long Beach
janet.muniz@csulb.edu

Abstract

Gentefication or gentrification by “the people” in Spanish is a term to describe Latinx-led commercial gentrification. This area of study has focused on displacement involving the loss of businesses, pushing out residents, and activist movements due to their neighborhoods’ threat of loss. Our research takes a different approach by solely focusing on business owners as the main drivers and participants in the *gentefication* of two Mexican-majority commercial districts in Southern California, Barrio Logan and Santa Ana. We conducted fieldwork and interviews to understand what types of business owners participate in *gentefication* and identify three groups: (1) locals, (2) newcomers, and (3) longtimers. We show how local and newcomer businesses, while on the surface present as “traditional” gentrifiers relative to longtimers, demonstrate heterogeneous motivations and narratives around participating in *gentefication*. By examining *gentefication* from the perspective of business owners, we unpack what has been previously understood as a monolith of actors.

Introduction

Commercial gentrification refers to the process in which local businesses experience an upward shift in social class (Pastak et al. 2019). This process often occurs alongside residential gentrification and results in both the direct and indirect displacement of low-income and working-class individuals (Marcuse 2015). Key features of commercial gentrification include physical improvements, such as new or upgraded infrastructure, and changes to the community's prevailing social and cultural dynamics (Lees et al. 2010). The key actors typically documented as driving commercial gentrification, especially in ethnic and racial communities, are outsiders—individuals from outside the ethnic group—primarily motivated by economic profit. But what happens when this is not the case?

Commercial *gentefication*—gentrification by “the people” in Spanish—happens when Latinx individuals establish new businesses alongside working-class locals, offering products or services that cater primarily to a new audience of middle- and upper-class consumers from outside the neighborhood who come to experience its culture. *Gentefication* complicates the dominant narrative of outsiders moving in to displace longstanding businesses as U.S.-born college-educated Latinx individuals return to the *barrio* as higher-class business owners working to preserve the culture of the area (Anderson & Sternberg 2013; Ahrens 2015; Dávila 2004; Delgado & Swanson 2019; González 2017; Huante 2021; Muñoz et al. 2024; Sarmiento 2022; Shmaryahu-Yeshurun 2024). Communities facing *gentefication* pose many contradictions as working-class residents and businesses are critical in maintaining the area's cultural integrity that, at the same time, are used to draw outsiders in (Ahrens 2015; Delgado & Swanson 2021; Huante 2021; Kosta 2019; González Romero & Seeley 2022). Thus, *gentefication* is a double-edged sword as it creates the opportunity for branding Latinx business owners' motivations as altruistic while at the same time providing an

avenue for the commodification of Latinx identity for profit as business owners exploit local culture for profit (Anderson & Sternberg 2013; Curran 2018; Dávila 2004; Gandhi & Minner 2017; Huse 2014). Prior studies have highlighted intra-ethnic tensions and conflicts between supporters and opponents of new Latinx businesses (Ahrens 2015; Delgado & Swanson 2019; Huante, 2021; Sarmiento 2022), arguing that these businesses commodify culture for economic gain in a way that ultimately replicates familiar patterns of white-led gentrification (Huante 2021; González & Seeley 2022).

In this study, we focus on Latinx business owners, highlighting the underexplored heterogeneity of the drivers of commercial *gentefication* in a way that challenges the assumption that commercial gentrifiers are outsiders—both geographically and culturally—to the areas where they establish their businesses (Hyra 2017; Lloyd 2010; Schlichtman et al. 2017; Zukin et al. 2009). More specifically, we address the gap in the developing *gentefication* literature by investigating a deeper and more nuanced understanding of the actors involved in *gentefication*, their motivations, and narratives regarding their businesses' involvement in this form of redevelopment.

We draw from fieldwork and in-depth interviews with business owners in the commercially *gentefying* business districts of two majority Latinx communities--Barrio Logan in San Diego, CA, and Santa Ana in Orange County, CA. Our case studies provide empirical evidence from business owners of *gentefication*'s expanding reach into further Latinx communities across the U.S., already well documented in large metropolitan areas such as Los Angeles and Chicago (Ahrens 2015; Anderson & Sternberg 2013; Huante 2021). Business owners provide insight into strategies for preserving neighborhoods' cultural character and community cohesion in light of redevelopment. Business owners' motivations for participating in *gentefication* are crucial for understanding their potential for (mis)alignment with the communities' consensus, documented in prior works as

highlighting intra-ethnic tensions and conflict between proponents of and activists against new businesses (Ahrens, 2015; Delgado & Swanson, 2019; Huante, 2021; Sarmiento 2022). Our data addresses the following questions: (1) What types of business owners participate in commercial *gentefication*? and (2) What are business owners' perceptions and narratives regarding their role in the neighborhood they are *gentefying*? Although the economic gain is a clear motivation for business owners who participate in *gentefication*—or *gentefiers*—we distinguish between different types through our nuanced analysis of their motivations to develop a typology of whom we categorize as: (1) locals, (2) newcomers, and (3) longtimers.

Our data demonstrates that owning a business in a *gentefying* community is viewed by “locals” or business owners who grew up in the area as an alternative to white-led commercial gentrification of their neighborhood that preserves local culture and community. At the same time, new business owners or “newcomers” who grew up outside of the area and sought out their business location due to economic opportunity and their excitement over its cultural regeneration. Therefore, while newcomers easily align with the discourse of cultural empowerment and broader struggles of the Latinx community, often emphasizing this in their businesses, it takes them longer to familiarize themselves with the neighborhood and its local history. However, their significant distinction lies in how their place of origin is framed in the social context, driving them to act in ways that avoid association with a stigmatized identity (e.g., gentrifier). While locals draw on community ties from their upbringing and justify their operations through their deep-rooted connection to the community, newcomers, lacking this deep-rooted connection to the community, integrate into local politics and actively celebrate the culture. For locals and newcomers, businesses in the *gentefying* area become intrinsically linked to cultural identity, which differs from longtime business owners, or “longtimers,” who may not explicitly participate in

gentefication but are subject to its effects. We still include longtimers in our typology as a reference point for business owners who express nostalgia for the community they once knew and are now striving to survive economically in the *gentefying* neighborhood.

Our typology is essential for engaging and categorizing each business owner in the *gentefying* landscape in line with their positions and motivations for participation instead of labeling all business owners as *gentefiers* that leverage cultural capital for profit. This typology is crucial for determining the best approach to engaging with each group and fostering community collaboration on three levels. First, identifying local *gentefiers* and business owners who grew up in the neighborhood and are familiar with its history, politics, and community needs can help foster more inclusive practices in collaboration with community members, activists, organizations, and policymakers. Second, unlike locals, promoting education and awareness among newcomers who move into the neighborhood is essential. Despite their commitment to contributing to the community, they often lack an understanding of its needs. Many also attempt to engage in local politics, sometimes to avoid criticism and resistance from residents and activists due to their outsider status.

Distinguishing between different types of *gentefiers* and their modes of engagement contributes to previous findings on the socio-political awareness of gentrifiers, as described by Brown-Saracino (2004), and highlights their efforts to balance personal reputation, ethics, and the stigma associated with gentrification (Parker & Ternullo 2024). Furthermore, it deepens the previous concept of “political *gentefiers*,” who mitigate the displacement effects of gentrification through activism (Shmaryahu-Yeshurun 2024). However, it does not eliminate tensions that may arise between longtime residents and business owners who rely on their community ties to justify their business activities in the neighborhood. Finally, it is crucial to distinguish between the group

we call local *gentefiers* and longtimers. Longtimers in Barrio Logan and Santa Ana present differently based on their community context, but at their core, are subject to coexisting with locals and newcomers actively mobilizing their businesses due to gentrification. **Latinx-Led**

Commercial Gentrification's Reach and Repackaging

Group-specific forms of coethnic commercial gentrification, also known as “gentrification of color,” disrupt the social and cultural dynamic of immigrant and ethnic neighborhoods (Shmaryahu-Yeshurun 2023). The disruptions exacerbate locals’ fears of detachment from their communities’ cultural heritage over time as their neighborhood no longer becomes recognizable and does not cater to them (Hom 2023; Huante 2021; Lin 2008; Munoz 2019; Orta 2021; Sarmiento 2022). Paradoxically, commercial gentrification can result in communities that lack the authenticity and culture that once drew outsiders to the area while also contradicting historical government-imposed economic neglect in favor of projects that draw in new consumers (Deener 2007; Martucci 2019; Zukin et al. 2009).

Gentefication is the colloquial term coined by the owner of a wine bar in Los Angeles’ Boyle Heights in 2011 to describe the commercial gentrification of working-class Latinx neighborhoods (Berestein Rojas 2011; González 2020; Herbst 2014). Since 2011, *gentefication’s* traction across Latinx communities in the U.S. has garnered significant scholarly attention through case studies of Chicago, New York, Los Angeles, San Diego, and Orange County. *Gentefication* transforms the commercial districts of once stigmatized working-class immigrant Latinx businesses into attractive spaces for leisure and commerce for a higher-income consumer base while increasing demand for “exotic” and “authentic” cultural products (Anderson & Sternberg 2013; Ahrens 2015; Curran 2018; Sarmiento 2022). Thus, as multiple aspects of Latinx culture are highlighted by businesses through food, music, art, and murals, these commercial corridors turn

into viable sites of “ethnic consumption” for the middle to upper classes of all racial/ethnic backgrounds (Anderson & Sternberg 2013). Hence, the commodification of Latinx identity via *gentefication* presents a twofold opportunity for business owners to capitalize off culture, space, and people and for people of that group to mobilize their resources for profit and mobility (Terzano,2014).

Gentefiers, or business owners who participate in Latinx-led commercial gentrification, coincide with the burgeoning Latinx middle class who seek out working-class neighborhoods to open their businesses (Aguis Vallejo 2012; Aguis Vallejo & Canizales 2023; González 2020; Valdez 2020; Vasquez 2011). Arguably, *gentefiers* present like traditional gentrifying business owners seeking out higher-income clientele (González Romero & Seeley 2022). A distinction between *gentefiers* is their altruistic motivation to “give back” to their communities (Aguis Vallejo 2012; González Romero & Seeley 2022). *Gentefiers* also have a history in neighborhoods similar to the ones they are *gentefying* if not from the city itself (González 2020). As a result, *gentefiers* also target the longtime working-class consumer or residential base of the communities where they open their businesses (González Romero & Seeley 2022). While *gentefiers* seek to preserve the culture and ethnoracial demographics of these communities, they are not exempt from contributing to the consequences (e.g., displacement of lower-income residents, stores, and services that working-class residents rely on) in these places and populations they seek to “give back” to (Delgado & Swanson, 2021; Rucks-Ahidiana, 2022; González Romero & Seeley 2022; Sarmiento 2022; Sims and Sarmiento 2023). At the same time, *gentefiers* can be politically active in their neighborhoods, advocating for affordable housing, inclusive planning, cultural identity preservation, or resisting displacement (Sandoval 2021; Shmaryahu-Yeshurun 2024). *Gentefiers* who grew up in the neighborhood can mobilize to contribute to the community and advocate for

its needs before policymakers, similar to Boyd's (2008) analysis of Black gentrifiers' motivations, which include community uplift and racial solidarity, as well as Pattillo's (2003) concept of the "middleman."

Research Gaps on Latinx-Led Gentrification

Gentefiers play a pivotal role in bolstering the symbolic culture of neighborhoods, directly and indirectly, contributing to planning and community engagement (Lung-Amam 2021; Sandoval 2021; Shmaryahu Yeshurun 2024). Yet, anti-*gentefication* scholar-activists have referred to *gentefiers* as "sell-outs" in the literature but have not directly studied business owners, highlighting an empirical gap in data used to make claims about the role of culture and commerce in *gentefication*. Instead, *gentefication* scholarship has provided empirical accounts from directly or indirectly displaced businesses or residents (Huante 2021), author-identified target consumer groups of businesses (González Romero & Seeley 2022) rather than asking the business owners directly about their desired customer, property owners and ethnographies of space (Sarmiento 2022), city documents and policies (Gonzalez & Lejano 2009). *Gentefication*, however, is distinct from, yet parallel to, and sometimes intertwined with residential gentrification occurring in affected neighborhoods, leading to either indirect or direct displacement. While we acknowledge the potential for commercial *gentefication* to result in the displacement accounted for by prior literature, we deviate from the *gentefication* literature's focus on outcomes. More broadly, commercial gentrification studies have also mainly focused on measurements of and changes in business ownership (e.g., using business directories at different periods) rather than qualitatively from the perspectives of the business owners themselves (Kosta 2019; Walker & Miller 2019; Zukin et al. 2009).

Prior work on Latinx gentrifying downtown commercial zones has primarily examined debates and advocacy responses among residents about the perceived value and detriment of *gentefication*. There is an opportunity to augment these foci by looking at heterogeneity in business owners participating in an area's *gentefication*. For example, in their literature review, Aguis Vallejo and Vasquez-Tokos (2024) find that the Latinx middle class is distinct and heterogeneous. Racialization, class origins, kin ties, and mixed legal status shape the experiences of the Latinx middle class (Aguis Vallejo & Vasquez-Tokos 2024) and the study of *gentefiers* who stem from this group. Latinx middle-class individuals that own businesses and mobilize their resources to capitalize on coethnic purchasing power have been identified as ethnoracial capitalists by scholars such as Aguis Vallejo and Canizales (2023), yet have been loosely applied to *gentefiers* (Santellano 2023).

In line with prior scholars who have categorized businesses in commercial gentrification, we develop a typology specific to *gentefication* from our unique qualitative accounts of interviews with business owners (González & Guiadana 2013; Kosta 2019; González Romero & Seeley 2022; Zukin et al. 2009). Our typology of *gentefiers* draws from Brown-Saracino's (2004) categorization of social preservationists and gentrifiers. Brown-Saracino (2004) calls social preservationists separate from gentrifiers as they “work to preserve the space they have entered: and have “a set of values that demand the presence of old-timers—with practice: they engage in efforts to prevent the displacement of old-timers in their area, despite acknowledging the disruption caused by their in-migration.” Instead, we show how under *gentefication* new business owners who can pass as what Brown-Saracino (2004) calls “social preservationists” are *gentefiers* in the same way as business owners who grew up in the community and returned to open businesses. These two groups, local *gentefiers* and newcomers add nuance to understanding *gentefication* as unique when

most participants are Latinx or seeking to preserve Latinx culture. While we know the possibility for the actions of the business owners in our study to displace the working class, their coethnic neighbors, and fellow business owners, as well as exploit culture, we cannot account for how much money they make, who their customers are or were, who they are displacing or pushing out with our data. Instead, we show how business owners justify their participation in *gentefication*.

Communities' Context

This study focuses on commercially *gentefying* Latinx communities—Barrio Logan in San Diego, California, and the downtown area of Santa Ana in Orange County, California (See Table 1 for demographic characteristics), which provide a significant comparative case study to understand commercial *gentefication* in Southern California (Lees 2012; Irazábal 2012; Yin 2003). We selected our case studies based on our prior research, geographic contexts, and access to business owners to understand how both communities' *gentefication* has similar and different dynamics. Despite the surge of commercial *gentefication* in Latinx communities across the U.S., our sites remain relatively under-researched as smaller suburban contexts outside the Los Angeles area.

[Table 1 here]

Barrio Logan is a working-class neighborhood in San Diego, CA, with a high concentration of Latinx residents, proximity (15 miles) to the U.S.-Mexico border, and a historical activist presence that centers on maintaining the area's cultural heritage and identity (Del Castillo 2007). The construction of Interstate 5 in 1963 and the San Diego-Coronado Bridge in 1969 displaced Barrio Logan residents and geographically divided the area (Sandoval 2021). Additionally, the reversal of a city council decision in 1970 to build a park under the San Diego-Coronado Bridge, which runs through Barrio Logan, sparked a community uprising, resulting in the establishment of Chicano Park, a significant site of community cohesion, culture, and art which was designated as

a National Historic Landmark in 2016, and in 2022, the Chicano Park Museum and Cultural Center was established (Chicano Park Museum and Cultural Center, 2022). The Barrio Logan Association (BLA) was established in 2014 as the advisory committee for the Barrio Logan Maintenance Assessment District (BL MAD) and promotes beautification and cultural development in the neighborhood. Barrio Logan's *gentefication* coincides with urban redevelopment policies and increasing real estate values in the greater San Diego area (Delgado & Swanson 2019).

The downtown business district of Santa Ana, California, is located 105 miles from the U.S.-Mexico border and is home to a shopping corridor with 48% Hispanic-owned businesses (US Census 2015). In the 1970s, the city of Santa Ana saw an increase in businesses owned by Mexican immigrants that catered to the working class and, in response, developed a plan that called for upscale housing and commercial space, which failed (González 2017). In 1984, Santa Ana established a business improvement district (BID) to promote its downtown through economic development, events, advertising, security, and maintenance (González 2017; Muñiz 2023). The 2011 demolition of the Fiesta Marketplace Plaza, built in 1989 to attract Latinx consumers, was replaced with new businesses targeting a higher-income clientele following the largest attempt at gentrification in 2007 via the Renaissance Downtown Specific Plan (González 2017; González Romero & Seeley 2022; Lodoño 2020). Finally, in 2015, Santa Ana City Council branded a new plaza and street signs with the Spanish name for its downtown street, *Calle Cuatro* initiating its *gentefication* (Molina 2015; Muñiz 2023; Muñiz et al. 2024).

Comparing Case Studies

As arts and culture destinations—Barrio Logan near the U.S./Mexico border and Santa Ana near significant tourist locations (e.g., beaches and Disneyland) play central roles in promoting their commercial sectors (González 2017). Barrio Logan and Santa Ana thus share many parallels to

elicit insight into *gentefication* from business owners who profit from its promotion. We identify the commercial *gentefication* of our case studies as follows. Barrio Logan's population of Latinx residents dropped from 83% in 2000 to 71% in 2019; in the same period, the white population grew from 6% in 2000 to 20% in 2019 (U.S. Census Bureau 2000, 2020). In contrast to these demographic shifts, 83% of the 77 businesses established in the last decade on Logan Avenue and 26th are Latinx-owned, according to mapping conducted by Author One. While Santa Ana's Latinx demographic has remained stable from 2000, 2010, and 2020 at 78%, the city has doubled its college-educated population from 9.2% in 2000 to 18.5% in 2020 as well as the median household income has increased from \$55,903 in 2000 to \$80,265 in 2020 (U.S. Census Bureau, 2000, 2020). Businesses in downtown Santa Ana during these periods went from overwhelmingly catering to working-class consumers at 53.5% in 2000 to a doubling in targeting middle-to-upper class demographics from 7.2% in 2000 to 15% in 2011 (González Romero & Seeley 2022).

Additionally, the number of white residents in downtown Santa Ana increased by more than 17% and the number of Latinx decreased by 16% from 2000 to 2010 (González & Sarmiento 2017). Regarding cities' role in facilitating commercial *gentefication*, Santa Ana has a public/private partnership that institutionalized economic development and privatized public space through business owners in charge of its programming (Lee 2015; Mitchell 2001). Santa Ana has also experienced more diversified forms of gentrification through city and private projects in multiple downtown plazas than Barrio Logan due to its longstanding Latinx population and the size of its commercial sector (González 2017).

Methods and Data

We conducted 85 semi-structured interviews with business owners with establishments in the service sector (travel agencies, hair salons, consulting), retail (clothing stores, jewelry, bookstore,

art galleries), food (coffee shops, restaurants, bars), and entertainment categories (owning a venue) (see Appendix A for demographics). We recruited using snowball and purposeful sampling by attending the meetings of various city, business, and activist-oriented organizations to build rapport, understand the community dynamics, and connect with relevant business owners. We used purposive sampling based on the knowledge gained from participant observation at meetings and events, identifying key business owners actively involved in the area's *gentefication*. Snowball sampling allowed us to reach additional business owners who may not have directly participated in business community meetings and events. Our interviews averaged sixty minutes and were conducted in English, Spanish, and *Spanglish*. We audiotaped and transcribed the interviews verbatim. Business owners' identities are anonymized for confidentiality following Institutional Review Board protocols.

We also conducted participant observations at various sites relevant to *gentefication*. In Barrio Logan, this included monthly meetings and events of planning groups such as All For Logan, the Barrio Logan Association, and the Chicano Park Steering Committee. In Santa Ana, data was collected at city council meetings, public comment forums, executive board meetings, and events for the two business organizations under Santa Ana's BID that collected funds from business license fees and oversaw re-distributing funds through cultural programming efforts and collaborations with local organizations to boost foot traffic and commerce downtown. We also observed the cultural, political, and arts events, including Chicano Park Day celebrations, national and cultural holidays such as *Fiestas Patrias* for Mexican Independence Day, *Dia de los Muertos* or Day of the Dead, "Walk the Block," "Art Walks," among others initiated by our interviewees, such as festivals, shows, art exhibitions, and workshops. While we do not directly draw from our observations in the findings of this paper, they assisted us with building rapport with our

interviewees, recruitment, understanding the context of relationships between business owners, and the history of conflicts within the communities. The information gained from our observations also allowed us to tailor our interview questions and engage with business owners outside of the interview space. This enabled us to maintain deep embeddedness through prolonged and consistent engagement across our two sites.

We used qualitative analysis software NVivo and Dedoose to code the data into themes. Our thematic analysis was deductive and inductive, guided by our initial theoretical frameworks and based on the patterns that arose from the data (Clarke & Braun 2016; Tavory & Timmermans 2014). It addressed differences and similarities in business owners' motivations, perceptions, and roles in both communities, aligning with our research objectives. Since this paper emerged from our individual case studies, we discussed our coding and common themes, including the area's histories, redevelopment projects, local politics, tensions, events, and types of business owners. We wrote memos and met regularly during the data analysis to discuss patterns, shared interview protocols, and coding schemas.

Authors' Positionality

The data we collected demonstrates our access to the two communities based on our identity categories, researcher affiliations, and historical dynamics. For example, Barrio Logan data was collected by a non-Latinx international scholar, who found their position to present challenges and opportunities in establishing connections with business owners. Despite initial barriers, the community was cooperative and welcoming. The outsider status and neutral stance encouraged open sharing from business owners, enhancing the researcher's understanding. Business owners in Barrio Logan were informed about the purpose and process of the research and two were involved

in reviewing the study draft and provided feedback. To foster an “ethic of reciprocity” (Corbin & Morse 2003), the author also volunteered at community events per business owners’ request.

The Santa Ana study was conducted by a Mexican American, a child of immigrant parents, who is bilingual and grew up two miles from downtown. Despite not visiting downtown due to their parents’ migrating to the U.S. as young children and internalized pressures to incorporate into the “mainstream,” valuable insights were gained from Santa Ana business owners who saw their participation in the study to give back. Interviewees often asked the Santa Ana study’s P.I. about their insider knowledge about the city (e.g., schools attended, neighborhood lived in, family history) to build rapport and trust, as well as their outsider role (e.g., not having grown up going to downtown Santa Ana businesses or events). Interviewees were constantly reminded of a researcher’s presence at every business group meeting, continually introducing the project goals and status of the project (Lincoln & Guba 1985).

Types of Businesses Owners in *Gentefying* Areas

Our findings highlight the distinct narratives, roles, and perceptions of various actors and present a nuanced picture of business owners participating in *gentefication*. We identify three types of business owners –local, newcomer, and longtimer–based on length of time in the neighborhoods, characteristics, motivation to establish a business in the neighborhoods, and their perceived role, and perceptions towards *gentefication* in their neighborhoods.

The Local Gentefier

Local *gentefiers*, business owners born and raised in the community, offer a unique perspective on commercial *gentefication*. Typically, they are college-educated adults who grew up in the neighborhood, left for education in their early twenties, and returned to start businesses. Usually, they also see themselves as integral parts of the neighborhood with a connection to family and

friends and a deep understanding of local history and politics. They perceive development, particularly the influx of corporations or outsider investments, threatening the local community's physical displacement and cultural and political suppression. Therefore, their motivation for opening a business and participating in *gentefication* extends beyond financial gain. They describe owning a business as a strategic response to the threat of non-Latinx gentrification and a means to uplift and empower their community. They also seek to represent a local (e.g., regional/neighborhood level) voice and identity, not just a Latinx one, by demonstrating solidarity with the surrounding community. Their perspective emphasizes proactive engagement, maintaining agency in countering the negative consequences of gentrification. Local *gentefiers* assert their role in shaping what they perceive as culturally inclusive, diversifying local resistance patterns by establishing businesses and striving to preserve the area's rich history and cultural identity amid the changing landscape. While they express solidarity with the community, they primarily focus on their businesses rather than local politics, believing their mere presence is a significant act of representation.

Bonnie is a middle-aged Chicana living in a work/live loft in downtown Santa Ana, a mixed-use redevelopment project to attract outsiders. Bonnie resides upstairs and operates a real estate business downstairs. She distinctly refers to herself as a "*gentefier*" and describes her role as follows:

there's this new term called *gentefiers* of the people just like myself who left and then returned with some cash and changed the scope of the downtown area. So, I'm going to say that my role is to change representation. I have to stand my ground against the multimillionaires that live next door [...] the trust fund babies that live adjacent to me, and think that I don't belong in my own neighborhood.

Bonnie considers her presence a protest against and sees *gentefication* as a way to assert her belonging alongside her gentrifying neighbors, acknowledging that her return to Santa Ana has also brought some financial resources. Local *gentefiers* like Bonnie are in a unique position,

proving they belong to the “trust fund babies” next door while distinct from them due to their local status and solidarity with local issues and the community. At the same time, local *gentefiers* must prove to locals that despite living in luxury lofts and owning businesses, they are just like them and not in solidarity with traditional gentrifiers. To navigate this challenge—local *gentefiers* distance themselves from traditional white “trust fund” gentrifiers and justify their gains from *gentefication* by leveraging their cultural and geographic roots, having grown up in the neighborhood where they returned. Local *gentefiers* present their presence as a political act in defense of traditional gentrification, even if they are not significantly involved in grassroots or city-level mobilizations against redevelopment. . Instead, local *gentefiers* in Santa Ana would uplift Latinx-specific issues by holding board member positions within larger nonprofits that are not unique to local issues. At times, local *gentefiers* in Santa Ana expressed specifically not joining or participating in anything at the city or downtown level so as not to be conflated with a traditional or newcomer-type gentrifier.

Local *gentefiers* also demonstrate a strong allegiance to their local and ethnic identity through their businesses. Omar, a bar and restaurant owner born and raised in Santa Ana, initially pursued a career in education. However, he was persuaded by his wife to take part in the changes happening in their hometown's downtown. Omar's business serves as a platform to highlight Mexican culture and Santa Ana, showcasing his deep connection to the community. When promoting his business on social media, Omar explains,

I would put the pictures and the images associated with this restaurant, and I would put, “[restaurant name] welcomes you to Santa Ana.” You know, not the other way around. And not saying, like, we own the city, it's like, no, this is done by *Santaneros* (people from Santa Ana) for *Santaneros* and everyone else.

Omar explains that the main purpose of his business is to demonstrate how he gives back to his local community. He emphasizes his local identity as someone who grew up in the area and aims

to show ethnic solidarity by opening a business. For instance, he legitimizes his decision to open a Latinx working class-based restaurant and bar in Santa Ana by highlighting his local roots. According to Omar, his business is not just a capitalist enterprise; it represents more than that. "Look, me existing is a political statement. For me, this place means a lot; it's a political statement, a point of pride, and unforgivably Mexican." Omar explains that as a local, he can unapologetically utilize his ethnic identity, family history, and history in Santa Ana, which newcomers cannot account for in their work. Omar and other locals use narratives of resilience and resistance, emphasizing how they embody local pride and push against the whitewashing of their community via traditional white-led gentrification by being "unforgivably Mexican." *Gentefication* provides a unique opportunity for local *gentefiers* to use their business as a point of pride that also pushes against outside efforts to change their community as Latinx locals have been able to mobilize enough financial resources to open businesses in locations that newcomers previously sought.

Local *gentefiers* discussed how they differed from newcomers and longtimers because they brought in new cultural aspects unique to them as people born in the community. Ricky, a local *gentefier*, was born and raised in Santa Ana. He was a business owner in another city area but decided to move downtown because "it was more of a vibe for what [business] was, a little Mexican cultural store." Ricky explains that while outsiders of Santa Ana saw its downtown development as positive, residents noted it was negative. Instead, he wanted to contribute to the change as a local *gentefier*, "everywhere else is talking good about Santa Ana. It's really positive. Yet here in Santa Ana, we're negative about it. What's going on? So we slowly wanted to see that change being positive. Dude, you gotta be so Santa Ana proud." Ricky explains that local *gentefication* is also facilitated by the city for him as a business owner, and he saw an opportunity to, rather than passively argue against the change, contribute to it in an agentic way. To people

who speak negatively about Santa Ana's *gentefication*, Ricky says, "when you're finally ready to accept it, you're going to realize that all this cool movement has happened without you." Ricky sees himself as a catalyst in the cultural shift that is happening via *gentefication*, and rather than be a passive observer; he is actively shaping the future of Santa Ana. The positive representation of both Latinx and local regional Santa Ana culture in the businesses of local *gentefiers* like Omar and Ricky demonstrates strategic resistance against non-Latinx commercial gentrification. This holds particular significance in Santa Ana, where urban development policy encourages cosmopolitanism in its commercial gentrification, including diverse ethnic business owners.

In Barrio Logan, local *gentefiers* express similar sentiments to Santa Ana, primarily against gentrification by large corporations, investors, and white-owned businesses. Recounting the history of the neighborhood and its deep-rooted connection to the community emerges as a significant catalyst that propelled the establishment of their businesses as a strategy to combat white-led gentrification and instead embraces *gentefication*. Luis, a 35-year-old business owner, founded a restaurant that combines innovative flavors with the traditional Mexican tastes of his youth. He shared his childhood experience in the neighborhood, particularly with restaurants and the vibrant cultural scene of Logan Avenue. However, with the decline of the neighborhood and the subsequent closure of businesses in later years, Luis and other business owners embarked on a mission to open establishments on Logan Avenue to revitalize what had been lost, as he describes,

About ten years ago you started to see a real redevelopment, not of physical buildings, but of the people themselves that said "We want the neighborhood that we grew up with." That's what attracted us to open business here, we are not only investing in our neighborhood, but investing in the future, developing the community. It's not gentrification, it's *gentefication* because we are the from the neighborhood doing this for the neighborhood. Our focus is to preserve our community and culture and keep large corporations from coming and setting up shop. Instead of just talking about it and saying: "we don't want gentrification," we invest in not having it. We're taking ownership and you're not going to move us. That's the only way we're going to be able to succeed.

Luis is motivated to establish a business as a local *gentefier* in pursuit of economic profit and to reclaim the neighborhood for its residents. Owning a business among local *gentefiers* is a form of resistance against non-Latinx commercial gentrification, leveraging and harnessing their capital to benefit people who grew up in the community. Similarly, Sofia, a 45-year-old boutique shoe store owner from Barrio Logan, views starting her business as an act of overcoming the obstacles those raised in marginalized neighborhoods face. Sofia sees her business as assuming personal responsibility, agency, and activism. Despite solidarity with the community and resistance to displacement, when asked about involvement in local politics, such as in the community planning group to promote affordable housing, Sofia responds that her and local *gentefiers*' contribution to the community and resisting its displacement is through their business,

Gentrification is here, what do you choose to do with it? Do you choose to let everybody else take over, or do you want to advocate, get informed, and find out how you can also be a part of it? We can be the victims forever and let our life go by. Honestly, to me, this is victimization...racism still exists, but I refuse to be a victim of that. You want to shut your door on me? I'll find three other doors to open...growing up here, I got into gang life, so for me, to come back as an entrepreneur, as an educated woman, as a positive role model that's already had an impact...I have a sense of responsibility, I am a voice for a lot of these people who can't speak up... we can fight in other ways.

To justify their presence and activity, locals rely on their sense of belonging to the community, emphasizing that their success as business owners is, in itself, a political act that benefits the community, as Sofia pointed out: *“to come back... as a positive role model that's already had an impact.”* Paradoxically, while they have the most knowledge and familiarity with the local community, its needs, and politics, they do not necessarily see themselves as obligated to be involved in it. For them, to establish businesses that not only navigate but also take ownership of *gentefication* for the benefit of the community. These local *gentefiers*, despite the challenges of redevelopment projects coming into Barrio Logan, strive for success, not because of it. Their role in opening businesses by participating in *gentefication* is a way to combat other forms of

development and a powerful means to preserve the community's unique identity, represent local voices and history, assert ownership of space, and, ultimately, reclaim it. Local *gentefiers* operate their businesses within a community they perceive as their own, in contrast to newcomers. Alongside their expressed solidarity, deep familiarity with the neighborhoods and residents, and a desire to improve their communities, local gentefiers are uniquely positioned within gentrifying areas in ways that newcomers cannot identify with, highlighting the importance of distinguishing between the two categories. This positioning and their connection to the community serve as a strong strategy to maintain their legitimacy in conducting business within the neighborhood, allowing them to differentiate themselves from other gentrifiers/newcomers and avoid criticism from activists and residents.

The Newcomer Gentefier

Alongside local *gentefiers*, newcomers, namely, business owners who are not part of the community and have come from outside, often from nearby diverse communities, some of which share cultural similarities with Barrio Logan or Santa Ana. They are typically young and educated and are motivated to open businesses by searching for economic opportunities in environments that they perceive as supportive and welcoming and embrace diversity and local culture. While newcomers easily align with the discourse of cultural empowerment and broader struggles of the Latinx community, often emphasizing this in their businesses, it takes them longer to familiarize themselves with the neighborhood and its local history. But the significant distinction between locals and newcomers lies in how their place of origin is framed in the social context, driving them to act in ways that avoid association with a stigmatized identity. The resemblance to traditional gentrifiers from outside the community, along with the fear of criticism, leads newcomers to adapt

their approach by assimilating into the local community, engaging in local politics, and representing Latinx culture.

Consequently, despite newcomers' surface-level familiarity with the community and its history, they profess solidarity, with some expressing significant involvement in local and urban community politics as a strategy to preempt or navigate public criticism of their involvement in its *gentefication*. As a result, newcomers in Santa Ana specifically navigate many competing terrains where they can address the criticisms and speculations from residents, local *gentefiers*, and longtime business owners. At the same time, newcomers actively work to stay on the radar of city governance and ongoing plans for development where they can find additional opportunities to expand their reach.

Stephanie, a 38-year-old bar owner, grew up in a working-class Latinx neighborhood in Los Angeles similar to Santa Ana. As a Latina, yet an outsider to the area, she was aware of its negative reputation. Stephanie's introduction to Santa Ana came through its bar scene and LGBT nightlife. A friend offered her the opportunity to own a bar, previously a gathering place for working-class Mexican immigrants or what she calls a “*paisa* bar” (*paisano* meaning person from your *pais* or place of origin in Spanish). The bar Stephanie owns today has not departed much from its “*paisa* bar” origin, she says,

I think we try to cater to the culture of Santa Ana and not change it. We're not trying to gentrify it. You know like per se so many other places or people who were, you know in the beginning, that was a big struggle. People are thinking we are trying to gentrify. but we're not. I think we keep that culture alive here.

Being culturally aware, informed, and thoughtful was a pattern demonstrated by newcomers in both Santa Ana and Barrio Logan. Stephanie explained that although her business used to be more “*paisa*,” meaning the customer base was homogenous working-class, she worked to demonstrate that her business had the same goal of maintaining Santa Ana's Mexican ethnic identity through

its new craft beer identity. A goal of newcomers was thus to enter the community with new businesses while leaving the cultural fabric. Stephanie highlights how newcomers navigate cultural awareness and informed decision-making around their business ventures and how they aim to open businesses aligned with the community's cultural context. Stephanie and other newcomers do not want to be labeled as "gentrifiers" despite being outsiders in Santa Ana and, therefore, embrace *gentefication*. Additionally, newcomers' outsider position leads them to adjust their way of fitting in with the local community, creating a narrative that integrates them into the cultural fabric while seeking economic opportunities. Newcomers ultimately strive to embrace, respect, and honor the rich cultural heritage of the areas they are *gentefying* as sometimes it is central to the appeal of their business location.

Similarly, Daisy is a Latina born and raised in the greater Orange County region, aware of Santa Ana's *gentefication* before participating. Daisy pivoted her original concept of a European grocery store, recognizing it as incompatible with Santa Ana's identity and culturally insensitive. Instead, she opened a boutique grocery store featuring items from the Southwest region that used "the border as a concept," aligning with the community's cultural context; she explains that despite her interests, they do not make sense for the area,

You know, I just love those, like, little French grocery stores or European grocery stores. And then I'm like, that's so fucking ridiculous to even consider doing here. And it's so stupid and tone deaf and like, not this city.

Despite her efforts to be culturally aligned with the people of Santa Ana, Daisy's store sells significantly more expensive items than the local downtown Latinx grocery store. These items, which include dry goods, ceramics, gifts, and artisanal crafts, are not only priced out of reach for many locals but also represent a form of cultural commodification as newcomers often capitalize on these cultural elements of the neighborhood. As profit-driven actors, Daisy and other

newcomers in Santa Ana incorporate symbols, icons, and representations of other cultures, hoping to attract additional customers. This marketing strategy, while it may align with Santa Ana's redevelopment projects that promote multicultural commercial gentrification by involving diverse business owners, tourists, and customers, is a clear example of a disconnect with the local working-class community. Despite the importance given by the newcomers to the Latinx cultural representation of businesses and the preservation of the neighborhood's identity, they are not necessarily catering to the local community. This represents a lack of connection and belonging to the local community, identifying them more akin to non-Latinx gentrifiers from outside the community. Paradoxically, to rationalize the business decisions she makes, Daisy discusses consulting with her network of Santa Ana locals to ensure she is not doing “tone deaf” work as she describes it. Daisy's store is also situated in a spacious corner of a new work/live loft project that remains unoccupied due to its unaffordability. The building is owned by the largest property owner downtown, who was accused of 'whitewashing' downtown Santa Ana in 2011 by locals similar to her neighbor Sarahi's business.

Sarahi is a Latina newcomer from a neighboring working-class Latinx community in Orange County. Sarahi first became involved in downtown Santa Ana as an artist working on a project through a grant, which she later developed into her business idea. Like other newcomers, she seeks not only to positively represent the culture in her business but also to be active and engaged in local politics. Sarahi mobilizes her cultural capital from the academic, art, and literary communities she is a part of as a writer and art-based activist to uplift local voices at events and exhibits she oversees. For example, Sarahi writes grants to pitch local youth literary programming, has curated social justice-based art exhibits downtown, and has created public art projects in and about the gentrification of Santa Ana, which has critiqued city planning and policy of the past.

Sarahi highlights how diverse strategies are required to navigate the complexities of neighborhoods facing what she describes as a pattern, “people of color are disappearing from downtowns across the nation- and we can't disappear. This country has a long history of making people disappear.” Sarahi explains that she would rather be part of a solution as an economic stakeholder in Santa Ana’s *gentefication* through her business and highlighting the community rather than the alternative, someone else taking the space and displacing Latinx culture. From this perspective shared by many newcomers in our studies, the redevelopment of Latinx communities is not a purely negative phenomenon but also an opportunity for economic mobility for business owners of color and from marginalized communities. However, their political and cultural discourse and activities tend to address the culture and struggles of the broader Latinx community and other cultures rather than the specific challenges faced by the local community.

Similarly, newcomers in Barrio Logan also incorporate cultural representations into their businesses, but unlike Santa Ana, these representations are almost exclusively of Latinx culture. Camila, a Latina who grew up in California, established her clothing studio to challenge the American beauty standard and empower Latinx culture and identity. She chose to open a shop in Barrio Logan as the community aligns with her identity and makes her feel comfortable, she explains,

My parents, they’re from Mexico. I knew I was American, and I was born here, but I didn’t have that representation outside [...] I always felt like I was too brown. So, for me to be around people that are representative of me is inspiring [...] one of my motivations for moving here was to be part of this community [...] In my business, I am very focused on adding that Chicano cultural aspect to the designs [...] Some of the phrases that I incorporate into my designs are “Brown Queen,” “Morena,” “Chicana,” and “Bonita”[...] I want people to have that sense of pride.

The celebration and empowerment of Latinx culture go hand in hand with economic profit and mobility for newcomers. Camila's clothing studio displayed jackets priced between \$110 and \$180, a vintage handmade jacket at a remarkable price of \$525. Camila addressed criticism around

commercializing culture for economic gain, "I know that some of my products are priced high. It's okay that not everyone can afford them. I've put a lot of effort into these handmade items, and I hope people appreciate supporting a Latina business owner." Newcomers like Camila perceived the use of culture as their legitimate right to advance mobility and opposed the presentation of it as a cynical exploitation and commodification of culture.

Furthermore, Camila is heavily involved in local politics, actively participating in community planning groups, collaborating with non-profit organizations, and organizing community lectures and fundraising events for community initiatives and local politicians. She explains her community work as a way of expressing gratitude to Barrio Logan for accepting her business there. Beyond positively representing the culture, newcomers engage in local politics and attempt to represent residents and their needs to avoid community criticism and to differentiate them from non-Latinx gentrifiers. In interviews, newcomers frequently used phrases such as "I want to give back to the community" and "This is an act of gratitude for them allowing me to be here." Similarly, for newcomer Daniel, the owner of a craft beer bar, his interactions with the Barrio Logan community strengthened his Mexican identity and connection to his culture, which he also represents in his business. Daniel reflects on attending a Latinx art show in Barrio Logan,

I saw all these people, Latinos doing cool things and cool music and it opened up in me, the realization that I don't see my culture positively reflected almost anywhere. I used to think that as Mexican-American you either remain a 100% Mexican who just happen to be living in the U.S., or you assimilate fully, become fully American. Coming to Barrio Logan helped me understand that there's a middle ground between those. When I started the brewery, I tried to fuse what's a United States craft beer tradition, but adding a Mexican component to it in flavors that we had grown up with. I joke that it's pride in a glass.

Like other newcomers, Daniel highlights a movement among *gentefiers* to reclaim and celebrate culture through business. *Gentefication* thus provides newcomers with the opportunity to bank on cultural elements they have expertise in that align with the local community. While local *gentefiers*

view opening businesses as a way to contribute positively to the community they grew up in and as a form of resistance against gentrification, newcomers see an economic opportunity for the community, themselves, and other business owners. Newcomers imply that their participation in *gentefying* the neglected neighborhoods of Barrio Logan and Santa Ana is not necessarily harmful as long as they are committed to seeing them flourish. As Daniel explained:

We support affordable housing, low-income housing. But how much is enough? A 100%? 50%? Do you run down your neighborhoods in order to drive down rents in order to make them undesirable and dangerous and awful places to live? That doesn't sound like a really good strategy either...when I was in college I thought of working at nonprofits... I remember one professor, lecturing us and he goes, you're idealistic, but you know what? You guys should go out, use your talents, make as much money as you can, but keep your values.. And he was absolutely right. So I changed majors and I went into international business management... fearing gentrification, is because you feel like you're always the victims and never the success stories. What if we figure out economic development strategies where we can all come up, make investments in our real estate and enjoy the benefits of our success?... some middle ground where we're going to evolve. We have to activate our economy.

Newcomers perceive *gentefication* beyond the discourse of participating in displacement; they see it as an opportunity to uplift communities that have suffered from prolonged neglect and provide a pathway for Latinx mobility. Due to their status as outsiders, despite sharing similar racial/ethnic backgrounds with the communities they are *gentefying*, some are involved in local politics and various organizations and initiatives. In contrast to local *gentefiers*, they cannot leverage deep familiarity with the community. Instead, they adopt strategies of belonging based on cultural identity, cultural representation, and engagement in local politics. Paradoxically, while newcomers attempt to be more involved in local politics, they are less familiar with the community and its specific struggles and are less aware/sensitive of urgent needs such as affordable housing. As a result, they are sometimes unable to effectively contribute to addressing local challenges or to be alight with community struggles. As newcomers navigate their place in the business community alongside local *gentefiers*, it is also essential to consider the experiences and perspectives of

longtimers who have witnessed the neighborhood's evolution over the years. We present longtimers as the counterpoint to newcomers and locals who, while not participating in *gentefication*, are still subject to it.

Longtimers

Longtimers have a deep-rooted sense of history and play a crucial role in shaping the core identity of the neighborhood, coexisting alongside local *gentefiers* and newcomers. Longtimers embody the enduring spirit of holding onto the area's history, especially among the elderly residents and immigrants from Latin America who migrated to the area in search of economic opportunities, much like the newcomers and local *gentefiers* of today. Longtimers are rooted firmly within the community, mostly aged 50 and above, and possess a wealth of knowledge about its history. Their ties to the neighborhood remain steadfast as they have increasingly become more involved and emotionally attached to what the *gentefying* spaces mean to them. For longtimers, opening a business at one time was a venture for profit and a means of survival, which is ongoing with *gentefication*. Their experiences, distinct from those of newcomers and local *gentefiers*, are not without challenges; they grapple with their neighborhoods' economic shifts and changing landscapes as they remain involved in community efforts by adapting. While they acknowledge the inevitability of change, they feel powerless to halt its progress while also being lumped in with newcomers and local *gentefiers* by people who do not understand them as separate because they collaborate in community spaces for the betterment of their commercial districts. We provide the category of longtimer as one that is community-specific and show how longtimers in Santa Ana, compared to Barrio Logan, are demographically distinct due to the unique history of each commercial sector but are a reference point for business owners, new and local, participating in *gentefication*.

Cindy is 64 and immigrated from Mexico with her husband in the 1980s. She opened a store in Santa Ana that catered to working-class immigrants by offering lines of credit for big purchases without a social security number or credit history. Residents and activists perceive Cindy and her husband as participating in and condoning *gentefication* because they collaborate with newcomers. Cindy explains,

It is hard to be an entrepreneur. I don't know why people think [...] How do you call it? *que somos* (that we are) gentrifiers? They see us like this, but it's nothing like that. Just hardworking people with a different mindset.

Cindy explains that longtimers in Santa Ana had to adapt their mindset from when they first arrived to survive *gentefication*. Cindy and her husband still sell the same items and cater to the same working-class population; however, they have become guided by newcomers in their involvement in the community to learn how to coexist with new businesses and their new upper to middle-class customers. For example, Cindy and her husband's business is a central organizing headquarters for longtimers who have hired a newcomer, Mariam, to help them maintain their presence in the business district. Mariam owns a consulting business. Mariam writes grants and attends conferences to learn strategies of other gentrifying and *gentefying* areas to keep longtimers current with communities across the U.S. Newcomers in Santa Ana have a similar person like Mariam for their businesses as well who is also a newcomer to Santa Ana from a neighboring Los Angeles County community.

A strategy longtimers used was to encourage residents of Santa Ana to come downtown, reminding them they are still there to cater to them despite its *gentefication* and increase in newcomers. Miriam explains her disagreement with residents and activists who believe in boycotting all businesses participating in or subject to *gentefication*. She explains,

To me, boycotting means that you're withdrawing your resources from your own community so that you're actually quickening the pace of what you're saying that you want

to actually protect it from. So, my strategy, and also other people that I talk to is, 'No. We have to do the opposite. You have to actually not boycott. You need to get everybody to come down from their own community to maintain the marketplace that says that it's for them.'

Miriam's strategy discourages residents' disengagement from the commercial sector altogether due to newcomers and local *gentefiers*. Instead, it has them see the heterogeneity of the businesses and the continued presence of longtimers. Residents' withdrawal from downtown Santa Ana businesses due to their perceived exclusion due to an increase in newcomers thus only worsens the marginalization of community-minded business owners like longtimers. Dan, an 81-year-old longtimer, has been actively involved in the business community through his shop and local governance. When asked about his thoughts on the current state of downtown Santa Ana as he has seen it over the years, he shared,

It hurts me. It hurts me greatly because I know looking at [a local redevelopment] Conference, that the same players involved in that, they're still-. I think they backed off a little bit when I started raising hell because the so-called "great amount of people coming" hasn't materialized yet. What they are doing- they're hurting a lot of the businesses that exist now [...] It's terrible.

Dan attends meetings and conferences, including the one mentioned above, focusing on the new redevelopment in Santa Ana. He believes that the emphasis on newcomers to the area is detrimental to longtime businesses. Dan has been deeply involved and invested in Santa Ana and has spoken out at city council meetings alongside other longtimers. The redevelopment conference he references triggered an emotional response based on his deep-rooted connection to the city. Like other longtimers, such as his friends Cindy and her husband, Dan has struggled to adapt to the numerous changes in Santa Ana over the years. These changes have often been promised as "progress" and commercial improvements but instead have been disruptive, requiring constant adjustment to the evolving landscape of the area.

Unlike Santa Ana, Barrio Logan depicts a natural turnover, with longtimers retiring or passing away and thus replaced by younger ones--newcomers and local *gentefiers*. In these cases,

newcomers and local *gentefiers* entered vacant spaces that were not in use due to economic decline in the neighborhood. Thus, newcomers and locals of Barrio Logan find themselves in a position that longtimers once did in Santa Ana. 95% of the 77 existing businesses on Logan Avenue opened in the last decade. Therefore, there are almost no longtimers in Barrio Logan in the same way as in Santa Ana. Respondents in Barrio Logan hardly discussed issues or tensions between old and new businesses in the same ways they did in Santa Ana. Hector is a 70-year-old grocery store owner who has been in Barrio Logan for many years,

Believe it or not, I have been here for 20 years, I saw all the changes here. My neighbors first were a pizza place, then barbeque ribs, and then sandwiches, and then a Mexican restaurant. A lot of people came and go, came and go [...] people got old and died. This is life [...] You see this sign? *'el barrio no se vende*. We don't sell the *barrio*. If you have a property here, if you are from the *barrio*, you don't sell it...the problem is that people die and the family, his kids sell it [...] the new generation think about money. It's not good [...] the businesses now are all not from here.

Hector highlights a deep-rooted presence in the community. As a longtimer in Barrio Logan, Hector has seen the progression of new establishments in the community's evolving commercial landscape, which underscores the transient nature of businesses and their constant flux. Hector also talks about not wanting to sell the *barrio* to outsiders among longtimers in Barrio Logan. However, the younger generation who take over longtimers' businesses sell the space to newcomers and returning young local *gentefiers*. For Hector, new business owners, even those who grew up and returned to the neighborhood, symbolize a new generation that has replaced longtimers in Barrio Logan. Longtimers ultimately provide insight into the resilience of business owners in commercially *gentefying* areas, demonstrating their unique challenges in the landscape of *gentefication* compared to newcomers and local *gentefiers*.

Discussion and Conclusion

In this article, we show how commercial *gentefiers*, a term we use to refer to business owners who actively participate in commercial *gentefication*, are not passive recipients of changes in their

commercial landscapes but dynamic and diverse participants. By owning a business in Santa Ana and Barrio Logan, our study participants see their role as agentic rather than passive to the implications of their commercial sectors' redevelopment while responding to historical and ongoing spatial injustices. Understanding the differences among business owners involved in *gentefication* is essential for this growing body of literature. Business owners' diverse dynamics shed light on the broader effects of commercial *gentefication*, emphasizing the unique narratives, perceptions and contributions of various participants: the local *gentefier*, the newcomer, and the longtime business owner.

Local *gentefiers* see themselves as agents in uplifting the neighborhoods' identity and history as business owners who grew up in the area. They view development positively only when it includes their participation and representation and describe it as a strategic response to the threat of non-Latinx gentrification and a means to uplift and empower their community. While local *gentefiers* are well-acquainted with the neighborhoods and communities surrounding their businesses and express solidarity with them, they are generally less involved in local politics than newcomers, relying on their deep-rooted presence and historical ties to the community to justify their role. Having grown up in the marginalized neighborhoods and successfully established a business, they see themselves as role models and frame their entrepreneurial activity as a political act of defending the community. Longtimers, on the other hand, express nostalgia and, thus, frustration with the ongoing redevelopment they have seen over the years and sometimes with newcomers' and locals' advancing of *gentefication* as well. Longtimers demonstrate fatigue from constant waves of change and prefer to maintain their established businesses instead of channeling their energies into broader community and city engagement.

Newcomers who perceive the development as beneficial are typically drawn to these areas because they are affordable and present opportunities to capitalize on their identities within a vibrant cultural landscape. They aim to run successful businesses that introduce unique offerings to the neighborhoods, attracting locals and outsiders. For these reasons, it is understandable why, unlike local *gentefiers* and longtimers, newcomers often seek to understand and engage with local issues to integrate better into the community and justify their presence. Lacking deep-rooted connection to these neighborhoods, they integrate into local politics and actively celebrate the culture in a way that helps them avoid association with a stigmatized identity. However, their unfamiliarity with the local context can lead to a superficial cultural representation that often lacks a deep-rooted understanding of local history and context.

Through our two case studies, we show how *gentefiers* narratives and perceptions for their participation have multiple meanings in their respective communities' contexts. In Barrio Logan, newcomers seek to focus on Latinx culture, while Santa Ana spans various cultural expressions, including food and artisan crafts alongside Latinx heritage. In Barrio Logan, the distinction between longtimers and newcomers becomes blurred, as aside from a few longtimers, most of the businesses in the studied area have been set up within the last decade. Here, locals actively attract newcomers, fostering a friendly environment contrasting Santa Ana's pronounced separation between longtimers, locals, and newcomers, some of whom have established roots for over fifty years. Barrio Logan has a rich history of activism against gentrification, with a strong emphasis on cultural preservation and thus the embrace of *gentefication* by both local *gentefiers* and newcomers. Conversely, Santa Ana's diverse demographic and history of urban development have created a different socio-political landscape, with varying anti-gentrification strategies and

ambivalence towards both *gentefication* and gentrification, with business owners rationalizing their work by emphasizing their role in preserving culture.

While analyzing the motivations and perceptions of local *gentefiers* and longtimers calls for engaging them in collaboration with activist organizations and policymakers for a more inclusive process in the neighborhood, the analysis also calls for education and outreach efforts regarding newcomers who, despite good intentions and activism, are less familiar with the community and its specific struggles, and seek to represent the culture and the Latinx community in general.

Business owners' participation in *gentefication* also poses significant challenges and tensions within the community. While we acknowledge the role of business owners in capitalism and neoliberalism, our study directly presents their complex motivations and actions, a viewpoint often overlooked in studies on commercial *gentefication*. This nuanced perspective is essential for understanding the dynamics of commercial *gentefication* in communities where it takes place as upwardly mobile Latinx individuals increasingly revitalize their communities as an alternative to white-led gentrification. Our data demonstrates how commercial *gentefication* weaves a complex tapestry of economic development, cultural preservation, and identity maintenance, highlighting the urgency and importance of the topic.

Finally, our study underscores the resilience of Latinx communities, their ability to adapt and navigate the challenges of *gentefication*, and their various strategies to address them. By engaging in *gentefication* and owning businesses, our respondents are not just shaping the future of their neighborhoods but also asserting their cultural identity and working towards economic and social justice. Business owners utilize *gentefication* and participate in it to their advantage, leveraging pride for their community and culture. As commercial *gentefication* continues to

reshape Latinx communities across the U.S., understanding the role of commercial *gentefiers* becomes crucial in understanding multi-faceted redevelopment that benefits its community.

References

- Ahrens, Mareike. 2015. "Gentrify? No! Gentefy? Sí!": Urban Redevelopment and Ethnic Gentrification in Boyle Heights, Los Angeles." *Aspeers* 8: 9-26.
- Agius Vallejo, Jody. 2012. *Barrios to Burbs: The Making of the Mexican American Middle Class*. Redwood City, CA: Stanford University Press.
- Agius Vallejo, Jody, and Stephanie L. Canizales. 2023. "Ethnoracial Capitalism and the Limits of Ethnic Solidarity." *Social Problems* 70(4): 961–980.
- Agius Vallejo, Jody, and Jessica Vasquez-Tokos. 2024. "The Latino Middle Class." *Annual Review of Sociology* 50: 521–46.
- Anderson, Matthew B., and Carolina Sternberg. 2013. "'Non-White' Gentrification in Chicago's Bronzeville and Pilsen: Racial Economy and the Intraurban Contingency of Urban Redevelopment." *Urban Affairs Review* 49(3): 435-467.
- Berestein Rojas, Rafael. 2011. "The Cultural Mashup Dictionary: Gentefication." <https://archive.kpcc.org/blogs/multiamerican/2011/12/28/7605/the-cultural-mashup-dictionary-gentefication/>.
- Brown-Saracino, Japonica. 2004. "Social Preservationists and the Quest for Authentic Community." *City & Community* 3(2): 135-156.
- Chicano Park Museum and Cultural Center. 2022. <https://chicanoparkmuseum.org/about/>.
- Clarke, Victoria, and Virginia Braun. 2016. "Thematic Analysis." In *Analysing Qualitative Data in Psychology*, 84–103. Sage.

Corbin, Juliet, and Janice M. Morse. 2003. "The Unstructured Interactive Interview: Issues of Reciprocity and Risks When Dealing with Sensitive Topics." *Qualitative Inquiry* 9(3): 335-354.

Curran, Winifred. 2018. "'Mexicans Love Red' and Other Gentrification Myths: Displacements and Contestations in the Gentrification of Pilsen, Chicago, USA." *Urban Studies* 55(8): 1711–1728.

Dávila, Arlene. 2004. *Barrio Dreams: Puerto Ricans, Latinos, and the Neoliberal City*. University of California Press.

Deener, Andrew. 2007. "Commerce as the Structure and Symbol of Neighborhood Life: Reshaping the Meaning of Community in Venice, California." *City & Community* 6(4): 291-314.

Delgado, Emanuel, and Kate Swanson. 2019. "Gentefication in the Barrio: Displacement and Urban Change in Southern California." *Journal of Urban Affairs* 43(7): 925-940.

Del Castillo, Richard G., ed. 2007. *Chicano San Diego: Cultural Space and the Struggle for Justice*. University of Arizona Press.

ERA. 2008.

<https://www.sandiego.gov/sites/default/files/legacy/planning/community/cpu/barriologan/documents/pdf/barriologanmarketanalysis1208.pdf>.

Gandhi, Akshali, and Jennifer Minner. 2017. "Economic Development Challenges for Immigrant Retail Corridors: Observations from Chicago's Devon Avenue." *Economic Development Quarterly* 31(4): 342–359.

- González Romero, Erualdo, and Tiffany Seeley. 2022. "Commercial Gentrification in a Downtown 'Made in Mexico': The Case of Santa Ana in Southern California, 1980–2011." In *Gentrification, Displacement, and Alternative Futures*, 86–106. Routledge.
- González, Erualdo R. 2020. "Latino Urbanism and the Gentrifying City." In *The Oxford Handbook of Latino Studies*, edited by Ilan Stavans, 175–196. New York: Oxford University Press.
- González, Erualdo R. 2017. *Latino City: Urban Planning, Politics, and the Grassroots*. Taylor & Francis.
- González, Erualdo R., and Lorena Guadiana. 2013. "Culture-Led Downtown Regeneration or Creative Gentrification?" In *The Routledge Companion to Urban Regeneration*, 536–547. Routledge.
- González, Erualdo R., and Carolina Sarmiento. 2017. "The Gentrification of Santa Ana: From Origin to Resistance." *PBS SoCal*.
- González, Erualdo R., and Raul P. Lejano. 2009. "New Urbanism and the Barrio." *Environment and Planning A* 41(12): 2946–2963.
- Herbst, Julia. 2014. "Guillermo Uribe on the 'Gentefication' of East L.A." *Los Angeles Magazine*, September 19. <https://www.lamag.com/citythinkblog/guillermo-uribe-on-the-gentrification-of-east-l-a/>.
- Hom, Lauren D. 2023. "Revitalizing Chinatown for a New Generation: The Community Politics of the Business Improvement District." *Journal of Urban Affairs*, 1-17.

- Huante, Alfredo. 2021. "A Lighter Shade of Brown? Racial Formation and Gentrification in Latino Los Angeles." *Social Problems* 68(1): 63-79.
- Huse, Tone. 2014. *Everyday Life in the Gentrifying City: On Displacement, Ethnic Privileging, and the Right to Stay Put*. Farnham: Ashgate.
- Hyra, Derek S. 2017. *Race, Class, and Politics in the Cappuccino City*. University of Chicago Press.
- Irazábal, Clara. 2012. "Beyond 'Latino New Urbanism': Advocating Ethnurbanisms." *Journal of Urbanism* 5(2): 241-268.
- Kosta, Ervin B. 2019. "Commercial Gentrification Indexes: Using Business Directories to Map Urban Change at the Street Level." *City & Community* 18(4): 1101-1122.
- Lee, Wonhyung. 2015. "The Formation of Business Improvement Districts in Low-Income Immigrant Neighborhoods of Los Angeles." *Urban Affairs Review* 52: 1-29.
- Lees, Loretta, Tom Slater, and Elvin Wyly, eds. 2010. *The Gentrification Reader*. New York and London: Routledge.
- Lloyd, Richard. 2010. *Neo-Bohemia: Art and Commerce in the Postindustrial City*. Routledge.
- Lees, Loretta. 2012. "The Geography of Gentrification: Thinking Through Comparative Urbanism." *Progress in Human Geography* 36(2): 155-171.
- Lin, Jan. 2008. "Los Angeles Chinatown: Tourism, Gentrification, and the Rise of an Ethnic Growth Machine." *Amerasia Journal* 34(3): 110-125.

- Gold, Steven J., and Ivan Light. 2000. "Ethnic Economies and Social Policy." In *Research in Social Movements, Conflicts, and Change*, 165-191. Emerald Group Publishing Limited.
- Lincoln, Yvonna S., and Egon G. Guba. 1985. *Naturalistic Inquiry*. Newbury Park, CA: Sage.
- Lung-Amam, Willow S. 2021. "Surviving Suburban Redevelopment: Resisting the Displacement of Immigrant-Owned Small Businesses in Wheaton, Maryland." *Journal of Urban Affairs* 43(3): 449-466.
- Lodoño, Johanna. 2020. *Abstract Barrios: The Crisis of Latinx Visibility in Cities*. Duke University Press.
- Marcuse, Peter. 2015. "Gentrification, Social Justice and Personal Ethics." *International Journal of Urban and Regional Research* 39(6): 1263-1269. Wiley Blackwell.
- Martucci, Sara. 2019. "Shopping Streets and Neighborhood Identity: Retail Theming as Symbolic Ownership in New York." *City & Community* 18(4): 1123-1141. <https://doi.org/10.1111/cico.12465>.
- Mitchell, Jerry. 2001. "Business Improvement Districts and the 'New' Revitalization of Downtown." *Economic Development Quarterly* 15: 115-123.
- Molina, Alejandra. 2015. "Downtown Santa Ana Concept Seeks Tie in to Latino Roots." *Orange County Register*. <https://www.ocregister.com/2015/04/08/downtown-santa-ana-concept-seeks-tie-in-to-latino-roots>.

- Muñiz, Janet, Ivis García, and Erualdo González Romero. 2024. "Cultivating and Defining Rights amidst Commercial Gentrification in Latinx Business Zones in Chicago and Santa Ana." *Planning Practice & Research*. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02697459.2024.2351759>.
- Muñiz, Janet. 2023. "Conflict and Co-Specialization on Calle Cuatro: How Placemakers Navigate Ethnic Branding." *Qualitative Sociology*. 1-20.
- Munoz, Lorena. 2019. "Cultural Gentrification: Gourmet and Latinx Immigrant Food Truck Vendors in Los Angeles." *Journal of Urban Cultural Studies* 6(1): 95-111.
- Orta, David. 2021. "Mexicans Built This Neighborhood! Gentrification, Organizations, and the Role of Place-Based Identity in Latinx Chicago." *Social Sciences* 10(8): 304.
- Parker, Jeffrey Nathaniel, and Stephanie Ternullo. 2024. "Gentrifiers Evading Stigma: Social Integrationists in the Neighborhood of the Future." *Social Problems* 71(2): 437-454. <https://doi.org/10.1093/socpro/spac026>.
- Pastak, I., Kindsiko, E., Tammaru, T., Kleinhans, R., & Van Ham, M. 2019. "Commercial Gentrification in Post-Industrial Neighborhoods: A Dynamic View from an Entrepreneur's Perspective." *Royal Dutch Geographical Society KNAG* 10(5): 588-604.
- Rucks-Ahidiana, Zawadi. 2022. "Theorizing Gentrification as a Process of Racial Capitalism." *City & Community* 21(3): 173-192.
- Sandoval, Gerardo Francisco F. 2021. "Planning the Barrio: Ethnic Identity and Struggles Over Transit-Oriented, Development-Induced Gentrification." *Journal of Planning Education and Research* 41(4): 410-424.

Sarmiento, Carolina. 2022. "Not Diverse Enough? Displacement, Diversity Discourse, and Commercial Gentrification in Santa Ana, California, a Majority-Mexican City." *Urban Studies* 59(9): 1782-1799.

Here is the updated list in Chicago style (15th edition):

Santellano, Karina. 2023. *Brewing Culture: How Latinx Millennial Entrepreneurs Negotiate Politics of Belonging*. PhD thesis, University of Southern California.

Schlichtman, John Joe, Jason Patch, and Marc Lamont Hill. 2017. *Gentrifier*. University of Toronto Press.

Shmaryahu-Yeshurun, Yael. 2024. "Beyond Displacement: Political-Gentefiers Planning Their Barrio and Claiming Space Ownership." *Journal of Planning Education and Research*. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0739456X241247331>.

Shmaryahu-Yeshurun, Yael. 2023. "Gentrifiers of Color: Class Inequalities in Ethnic/Racial Neighborhood Displacement." *Journal of the American Planning*. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01944363.2023.2251981>.

Sims, J. Revel, and Carolina S. Sarmiento. 2023. "Squeezed In and Pushed Out: Dual and Contradictory Displacements in Santa Ana, CA." *City* 27, no. 3–4: 294–320. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13604813.2023.2207248>.

Tavory, Iddo, and Stefan Timmermans. 2014. *Abductive Analysis: Theorizing Qualitative Research*. University of Chicago Press.

- Terzano, Kathryn. 2014. "Commodification of Transitioning Ethnic Enclaves." *Behavioral Sciences* 4, no. 4: 341–351.
- U.S. Census Bureau. 2000, 2010. "Social Explorer Fact Sheet—Table-SE: T13." <https://www.socialexplorer.com/data/C2020/documentation>.
- Valdez, Zulema. 2020. "The Great Recession and Precarious Wealth Among Middle-Class Mexican-Origin Entrepreneurs." *Journal of Ethnic and Migration Studies* 46, no. 18: 3874–91.
- Vasquez, Jessica. 2011. *Mexican Americans Across Generations: Immigrant Families, Racial Realities*. New York: NYU Press.
- Yin, Robert K. 2003. *Case Study Research: Design and Methods*. 3rd ed. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage.
- Walker, Samuel, and Chloe Fox Miller. 2019. "Have Craft Breweries Followed or Led Gentrification in Portland, Oregon? An Investigation of Retail and Neighborhood Change." *Geografiska Annaler: Series B, Human Geography* 101, no. 2: 102-117.
- Zukin, Sharon, Valerie Trujillo, Peter Frase, Danielle Jackson, Tim Recuber, and Abraham Walker. 2009. "New Retail Capital and Neighborhood Change: Boutiques and Gentrification in New York City." *City & Community* 8, no. 1: 47-64.

Tables

Table 1. Santa Ana and Barrio Logan Neighborhood Characteristics

<i>Variable</i>	<i>Neighborhood</i>	
	<i>Santa Ana*</i>	<i>Barrio Logan</i>
Total population	49,008	4,234
Median household income	\$57,796	\$45,281
Mean age	30.2	31.4
Race and Ethnicity		
% Latino/Hispanic	86.8	60
% White	7.2	26
% Asian	4.4	2.8
% Black	0.8	9.1
% Other	1.5	2.1
% Foreign-born	41.4	21.6
% College graduate	11.5	30.7
% Unemployed	3.4	15.8
% Of households below poverty	17.8	28.3

Household	12,341	1,235
-----------	--------	-------

Source: U.S. Census Bureau, 2016-2020 American Community Survey five-year estimates.

*Accounts for downtown Santa Ana 92701 zip code only

Appendix A. Business Owners' Demographics

<i>Variable</i>	<i>Neighborhood</i>		
	<i>Santa Ana</i>	<i>Barrio Logan</i>	
Gender	% Male	58	60
	% Female	42	40
Average age	49	39	
Place of birth	% Born in neighborhood	0*	14
	% Born in the city	42	40

	% Born in the USA	91	21
	% Born in Mexico	9	22
Income	% Middle-class	98	95
	% College graduate	49	40
Property Status	% Owner Occupied	28	7
	% Renter Occupied	72	93
<hr/>			
<i>N</i>		43	42
<hr/>			

*Santa Ana does not have comparable residential geographies to Barrio Logan for people to have been born or live in the downtown area specifically.